

EVALUATION OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN PRE-ECLAMPSIA**Mirzaeva Gulchehra Payzullaevna
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17312149>**

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INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON
SCIENCE, EDUCATION &
LAW

Scientific Open Access Conference

ARTICLE INFOReceived: 01st October 2025Accepted: 04th October 2025Online: 10th October 2025**KEYWORDS**

Pre-eclampsia is a multisystem disorder of pregnancy, typically developing after 20 weeks of gestation, marked by new-onset hypertension and proteinuria, or evidence of maternal organ dysfunction.

ABSTRACT

Pre-eclampsia (PE) is a hypertensive disorder unique to pregnancy, characterized by systemic endothelial dysfunction leading to multi-organ involvement. Among the affected organs, the kidneys play a pivotal role both in the pathogenesis and in clinical manifestations. This review discusses the mechanisms of renal dysfunction in pre-eclampsia, current diagnostic methods including biochemical and Doppler parameters, and their clinical significance in evaluating disease severity and predicting outcomes. Understanding renal changes in pre-eclampsia aids in early detection, improved monitoring, and prevention of complications for both mother and fetus..

Pre-eclampsia is a multisystem disorder of pregnancy, typically developing after 20 weeks of gestation, marked by new-onset hypertension and proteinuria, or evidence of maternal organ dysfunction. It affects approximately 5–8% of pregnancies globally and remains a leading cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality.

The renal system is significantly involved in pre-eclampsia, both as a target and a mediator of pathophysiological changes. Renal dysfunction results from widespread endothelial activation, vasospasm, and altered glomerular permeability. Evaluation of renal impairment is therefore essential for disease staging, prognosis, and therapeutic decision-making.

Materials and Methods: The first stage of the study included 122 pregnant women, of whom 46 (37,7%) had chronic kidney disease (CKD). The aim of the second stage was to find a differential diagnostic criterion between CKD and PE. Among the 122 patients, 36 were diagnosed with PE. The third stage included an additional 16 pregnant women with CKD. Based on the differential diagnostic criterion and pregnancy outcomes, 138 patients were divided into three groups, with 14 women from the comparison group transferred to the main group: Group I (main) — 66 (47,8%) patients with the development of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy (1st subgroup — 30 (21,7%) women with CKD, 2nd subgroup — 36 (26,1%) patients without CKD); Group II (comparison) — 32 patients with CKD without hypertensive disorders; Group III (control) — 40 women with a physiological course of this pregnancy and an uncomplicated reproductive history.

A clinical and laboratory examination of all participants was conducted, measuring the levels of sFlt-1, PlGF, S-endoglin, cystatin C, KIM-1, podocalyxin, α 1- and β 2-microglobulin.

Results: ROC curve analysis showed that the threshold concentration of sFlt-1 to distinguish PE from CKD is 7715 pg/ml (sensitivity — 97%, specificity — 96%), while for PlGF it is 88.15 pg/ml (sensitivity — 90%, specificity — 100%). The threshold value of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio is 150,25 (sensitivity — 100%, specificity — 100%). The method for determining the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio exhibits the highest sensitivity and specificity, with maximum accuracy (94%) and significant negative predictive value (95,4%).

Conclusion: The value of sFlt-1/PlGF \geq 150,25 may serve as a differential diagnostic criterion for PE in patients with arterial hypertension and clinically significant proteinuria. We suggest that the use of the differential diagnostic criterion identified by us (measurement of the studied markers in peripheral blood and urine) may be effective both for diagnosing already developed PE and for predicting its occurrence.

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